

Synthetic Gonadogens. Part III. Synthesis of 4-(2'-Methyl-5'-ketocyclohexyl)-2-(4''-ketocyclohex-2''-enyl)-butane^a

V. S. Gaiind*, S. P. Narula, C. Swaroop, and S. M. Mukherji**

Synthesis of the compound, named in the title, has been achieved through the use of the Birch-Wilds method of reduction.

In continuation of our previous work (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 765) we have carried out the synthesis of 4-(2'-methyl-5'-ketocyclohexyl)-2-(4''-ketocyclohex-2''-enyl)-butane^a (X). This structure is considered to be the ring B-C open analogue of physiologically active D-homosteroid androgens (Shoppee, "Chemistry of Steroids", Butterworth Scientific Publications, 1958, p. 155). The report by Blanchard *et al.* (*Endocrin.*, 1943, 32, 307; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1579) on the estrogenic activity of 1-(*m*-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)-hexane, coupled with the transformation of 19-nortestosterone on aromatisation of ring A into the estrogen, estrone, and further, the observation that the absence of Δ^4 -unsaturation as in dihydrotestosterone and 17- α -methyl-dihydrotestosterone (Rubin *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 292) does not diminish the androgenic activity, suggest the desirability of synthesising hydroaromatic structures of type (X).

The starting material, 4-methylcyclohex-2-enone (I), was obtained essentially according to Wilds and Nelson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5360).

The reaction sequence employed is illustrated as follows :

*Present address: Punjab Engineering College, Chandigarh.

**Present address: University College, Kurukshetra, Punjab

hexyl]-ethyl methyl ketone (VIe) in 37% yield. By this method it was difficult to obtain the pure ketone because of the proximity of the boiling points of the nitrile and the ketone.

Alternatively, for obtaining the pure ketone (VIe), potassium β -[2-methyl-5-keto-(5-dioxolane)-cyclohexyl]-propionate (VIc) was prepared by hydrolysis of the nitrile (VIb) with 20% EtOH-KOH in 68.4% yield. The potassium salt (VIc) was converted into the acid chloride (VI d) by the action of oxalyl chloride in benzene (cf. Adams and Ulich, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 605); yield was not recorded because the chloride tended to decompose on distillation. The crude compound (VI d) was subsequently treated with cadmium-dimethyl in benzene at the reflux temperature according to the method of Cason and Prout (*ibid.*, 1944, **66**, 46) to obtain (VIe) in 73.1% yield.

The ketal-ketone (VIe) was subsequently allowed to react with *p*-anisylmagnesium bromide in anhydrous sulphur-free benzene to obtain the intermediate carbinol (VII) (not isolated), which on distillation in presence of an iodine crystal furnished 4-[2'-methyl-5'-keto-(5'-dioxolane)-cyclohexyl]-2-*p*-anisyl-2-butene (VIII) in 45% yield. The olefine (VIII) was subjected to lithium-alcohol-anhydrous ammonia reduction and the hydro derivative (IX) was hydrolysed and isomerised with 5% hydrochloric acid (cf. Wilds and Nelson, *loc. cit.*) to obtain 4-(2'-methyl-5'-keto-cyclohexyl)-2-(4'-keto-cyclohex-2'-enyl)-butaneⁿ (X) as a pallid viscous liquid in 45% yield.

*EXPERIMENTAL

(a). *Diethyl (3-Oxo-6-methylcyclohexyl)-malonate* (II).—To sodium ethoxide (from 1.5 g. of sodium) was introduced, in the cold and to the exclusion of moisture, freshly distilled diethyl malonate (32 g.) 4-Methylcyclohex-2-enone (22 g.), dissolved in minimum quantity of anhydrous ether, was added dropwise with vigorous shaking in $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The reaction mixture was kept at about 0° for 50 hours and then acidified with glacial acetic acid. The organic layer was extracted with ether; the ethereal extract was washed once with water, twice with dilute sodium carbonate solution, and again with water until washings were neutral to litmus. After drying (anhyd. Na₂SO₄) and removal of the ether, the residue was distilled *in vacuo* to obtain a yellowish mobile liquid, b.p. 167°/6 mm, yield 55.5%. (Found: C, 62.27; H, 8.11. C₁₄H₂₂O₂ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.2%).

The *semicarbazone* of (II), prepared by the usual procedure, was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 154°. (Found: N, 12.79. C₁₅H₂₅O₃N₃ requires N, 12.84%).

(b). Potassium butoxide^t (7.8 g.) was cooled to 0° and diethyl malonate (32 g.) was added dropwise with shaking. 4-Methylcyclohex-2-enone (22 g.) was introduced gradually with shaking. The reaction mixture after having been kept at room temperature for about 20 hours was acidified with glacial acetic acid. After working up as in (a), ester (II) was obtained as a pallid oil, yield 4 g.

3-Oxo-6-methylcyclohexylacetic Acid (IIIa).—A mixture of the preceding ester (20 g.), HCl (40 c.c., *d* 1.19), and water (160 c.c.) was refluxed for 10 hrs. After removal of HCl under reduced pressure, water (50 c.c.) was added to the residue; the organic material was

*M. p.'s and b. p.'s uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Straus, Oxford.

taken up in ether and dried (anhyd. Na_2SO_4). On removal of the solvent, the residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure, yield 10 g. (50%), b.p. $164-66^\circ/8\text{mm}$. (Found: C, 63.20; H, 21. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 63.51; H, 8.29%).

Ethyl (3-Oxo-6-methylcyclohexyl)-acetate (IIIb).—A mixture of the acid (IIIa) (20 g.), absolute ethanol (8 g.), anhydrous benzene (100 c.c.), and H_2SO_4 (conc., 1 c.c.) was refluxed in a Dean and Stark apparatus till no more water had separated. The mixture was cooled and the organic material was taken up in ether-benzene. After working up in the usual manner, the ester (IIIb) was obtained as a yellow oil, b.p. $129-30^\circ/8\text{mm}$, yield 20 g. (Found: C, 66.22; H, 9.23. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 66.64; H, 9.15%).

Its *semicarbazone* was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 145° . (Found: N, 16.43. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 16.46%).

Its *2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared by the sulphuric acid method as deep orange needles (ethanol), m.p. 138° . (Found: N, 14.56. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.81%).

Ethyl [3-Oxo-(3-dioxolane)-6-methylcyclohexyl]-acetate (IV).—A mixture of the ester (IIIb) (20 g.), ethylene glycol (7 g.), anhydrous benzene (200 c.c.), and P.T.S. (0.2 g.) was refluxed under a constant water separator (Dean and Stark type) until no more water had collected (8 hrs.). The reaction mixture was cooled, the excess of P.T.S. was destroyed with a little sodium ethoxide in ethanol, and sufficient amount of water was added. The organic phase was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed with water and dried (anhyd. Na_2SO_4). Distillation of the product under reduced pressure, after removal of the solvent, furnished 20 g. (84%) of a yellow oil boiling at $135^\circ/5\text{mm}$. (Found: C, 64.6; H, 9.02. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 64.44; H, 9.15%).

β -(3-Oxo-6-methylcyclohexyl)-ethyl Alcohol (Va).—A slurry of LiAlH_4 (1.4 g.) in anhydrous ether (100 c.c.) was placed in a 500 c.c. three-necked flask, equipped with a glycerol-sealed mechanical stirrer, an addition funnel, and a reflux condenser fitted with CaCl_2 drying tube. A solution of the ester (IV) (16 g.) in dry ether was added with efficient stirring to maintain the ether at gentle reflux. The contents were then refluxed for 1 hour, cooled, treated with water (10 c.c.), and then with 20% H_2SO_4 (100 c.c.). The organic material was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed successively with water, NaHCO_3 solution, and water and dried (anhyd. Na_2SO_4). After removing the solvent, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to obtain a light, colorless oil, b.p. $120^\circ/12\text{mm}$, yield 12 g. (75%). (Found: C, 69.17; H, 10.13. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 69.19; H, 10.32%).

β -(3-Oxo-6-methylcyclohexyl)-ethyl Bromide (Vb).—To a cooled solution of (Va) (20 g.) in anhydrous benzene (20 c.c.) with three drops of dry pyridine was added phosphorus tribromide (15 g.) during 5 mins. The mixture was allowed to attain room temperature and kept there for another $1\frac{1}{4}$ hrs. It was finally heated at $60-65^\circ$ for about 1 hour, cooled, and then poured into ice-water. The organic substance was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed successively with water, cold dilute NaHCO_3 solution (5%), and water and dried. On removal of the solvent the residue was fractionated from a Claisen head, when the bromide (Vb) was obtained as a yellow mobile liquid, b.p. $137-40^\circ/7\text{mm}$, yield 28.8 g. (80%). (Found: C, 49.03; H, 6.82; Br, 36.33. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{OBr}$ requires C, 49.31; H, 6.84; Br, 36.53%).

β -[3-Oxo-(3-dioxolane)-6-methylcyclohexyl]-ethyl Bromide (VIa).—A mixture of the compound (Vb) (20 g.), ethylene glycol (7 g.), anhydrous benzene (200 c.c.), and P.T.S. (0.2 g.) was treated as before to obtain the ketal bromide (VIa) as an oil, b.p. 138-40°/6mm, yield 20 g. (84%). (Found: C, 50.17; H, 7.29; Br, 30.11. $C_{11}H_{19}O_2Br$ requires C, 50.19; H, 7.22; Br, 30.41%).

β -[3-Oxo-(3-dioxolane)-6-methylcyclohexyl]-ethyl Cyanide (VIb).—To a solution of potassium cyanide (4.6 g.) in water (10 c.c.) was added gradually, with stirring and to the exclusion of moisture, the preceding bromide (VIa) (15 g.) mixed in 95% ethanol (20 c.c.) during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The mixture was refluxed for 24 hours, filtered under suction, and the residue was washed with ethanol (10 c.c. $\times$ 2). Most of the solvent was distilled. The residual mixture was then poured into ice-water and the organic material was extracted with ether. From the ethereal solution after removal of the solvent, compound (VIb) was obtained in 9 g. yield (81.8%), b.p. 120°/7 mm. (Found: C, 68.72; H, 9.14; N, 6.63. $C_{12}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 68.86; H, 9.15; N, 6.69%).

β -[3-Oxo-(3-dioxolane)-6-methylcyclohexyl]-ethylmethyl Ketone (VIe).—A solution of methylmagnesium iodide was prepared from dry magnesium turnings (1.2 g.), methyl iodide (7 g.), and anhydrous ether (30 c.c.). To this was added, under cooling, the compound (VIb) (10 g.), dissolved in dry ether (10 c.c.). Most of the ether was replaced by dry sulphur-free benzene (40 c.c.). The contents were refluxed for 6 hours on a steam bath. The Grignard complex was hydrolysed with aqueous ammonium chloride; the benzene layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted thoroughly with ether. The combined extract was washed with water repeatedly and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed and the residue was distilled in vacuum to obtain 4 g. (37%) of the ketone (VIe) as a mobile colorless oil. (Found: C, 69.11; H, 7.78. $C_{13}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 68.99; H, 9.8%).

The bis-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrozone of (VIe) was crystallised from ethyl acetate-ethanol mixture, m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 19.23. $C_{25}H_{30}O_9N_8$ requires N, 19.11%).

β -[2-Methyl-5-keto-(5-dioxolane)cyclohexyl]-propionyl Chloride (VIc).—A mixture of the above cyanide (VIb) (30 g.) and 20% ethanolic KOH (100 c.c.) was refluxed for 25-30 hours until the evolution of ammonia stopped. Ethanol and water were evaporated. Last traces of water were removed in a vacuum desiccator. The residual solid K salt (VIc) weighed 26 g. (68.4%).

To a solution of oxalyl chloride (17.7 g.) in dry benzene (35 c.c.) was dropped the above potassium salt (VIc) (26 g.) in small portions so as to keep the evolution of gases under control. The mixture was then refluxed for 2 hours and the solid matter was filtered. The acid chloride (a test portion) tended to decompose during vacuum distillation. The crude material weighed 22.4 g. (93%).

β -[3-Oxo-(3-dioxolane)-6-methylcyclohexyl]-ethylmethyl Ketone (VIe).—To methylmagnesium iodide, prepared from clean dry Mg turnings (2.6 g.), MeI (15.4 g.), and dry ether (60 c.c.), was introduced anhydrous cadmium chloride (8.7 g.) in small lots under cooling and stirring. The mixture was then refluxed with stirring for 3 to 4 hrs. Ether was completely replaced by benzene (150 c.c.) and the solution heated to boiling. The acid chloride (VIc) (22.4 g.) was then added with stirring at a rate so as to maintain the benzene at gentle reflux. The contents were then refluxed, stirred for about 1 hour, and cooled, when a hard solid was deposited. The mixture was then decomposed with ice-cold water.

The organic material was taken up in ether-benzene; the organic phase after drying and removing the solvent furnished (VIe) as a light mobile oil, b.p. 137°/7mm, yield 15 g. (73%). (Found: C, 69.11; H, 9.78. $C_{13}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 68.99; H, 9.8%).

The *bis*-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 148°; mixed m.p. with sample derived from the ketal-ketone (VIb), 148°.

4-[2'-Methyl-5'-keto-(5'-dioxolane)-cyclohexyl]-2-p-anisyl-2-butene (VIII).—To the Grignard reagent, prepared from Mg (2 g.) and *p*-bromoanisole (15 g.) in dry ether (100 c.c.), was added the preceding ketone (VIe) (15 g.) slowly under ice-cooling. The contents were allowed to stand overnight at room temperature and then refluxed for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was decomposed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The oily product was extracted with ether. After drying and removal of the solvent, the residual material was distilled in presence of a crystal of iodine to obtain (VIII) as a yellowish oil, b.p. 160°/6 mm, yield 10.58 g. (50%).

4-(2'-Methyl-5'-ketocyclohexyl)-2-(4"-ketocyclohex-2"-enyl)-butane (X).—A solution of the olefine (VIII) (9.9 g.) in anhydrous ether (20 c.c.) was placed in a 500 c.c. three-necked flask fitted with a glycerol-sealed mechanical stirrer, a soda-lime drying tube, and an addition funnel. Liquid ammonia (150 c.c.) was run into the flask and the stirring commenced. Freshly cut lithium metal (1.75 g.) was added gradually with stirring during 15 mins. Stirring was continued for 10 mins. more and anhydrous ethanol (13.0 g.) was added dropwise in 15 mins., when the blue colour was discharged. The ammonia was then removed, water and ether were added, and the mixture was left for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The organic material was extracted with ether. Removal of the ether left the dihydro derivative (IX) as an oily liquid, which was hydrolysed with 5% EtOH-HCl (40 c.c.) at water bath temperature for 2 hrs. Ethanol was then removed and the residual mixture was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed free of acid, dried, the solvent removed, and vacuum distilled to afford a yellowish viscous oil, b.p. 158°/6mm, yield 3.6 g. (45%).

The compound (X) gave a *bis*-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrozone which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-ethanol in orange red needles, m.p. 151°. (Found: N, 18.01. $C_{29}H_{34}O_9N_6$ requires N, 18.01%).